

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE READING IN ENGLISH

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ОБУЧЕНИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНОМУ ЧТЕНИЮ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Abstract

This article describes the basic principles of communicative reading. The general position of communicative reading, the basics of its study and teaching are described. Special attention is given to communicative reading in the study of foreign languages, in particular English.

Аннотация

В данной статье описываются основные принципы коммуникативного чтения. Описываются общее положение коммуникативного чтения, основы его изучения и обучения, отдельное внимание уделяется коммуникативному чтению в изучении иностранных языков, в частности английского.

Keywords: communicative reading, types of communicative reading, text component, reading speed, speech situation.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативное чтение, виды коммуникативного чтения, текстовый компонент, скорость чтения, речевая ситуация.

There is a large number of nuances of learning a foreign language, such as grammar, speaking, listening, writing, and reading. The study of foreign languages contributes to the unified speech formation of a person. Reading is one of the main varieties of speech activity. It can act as both a goal and a means of learning. With the help of reading, a person joins the scientific and cultural achievements of mankind, gets acquainted with art, as well as the life of other peoples. Reading has a tremendous impact on the development of the individual. With the help of reading, active as well as passive lexical baggage of words is enriched, grammatical skills are formed. The term "communicative reading" means mature reading, characterized by the automation of reading techniques, as well as a significant degree of formation of receptive lexical and grammatical abilities, as well as receptive skills to receive massive, as well as semantic information, which guarantees the focus of interest in obtaining cultural information of geographical, historical, socio-political, ethno-linguistic and ethno-psychological character from a foreign literary text [1].

Usually in communicative reading, 5 groups of skills were emphasized, which provide an absolute representation of the content and meaning of the text:

- skills aimed at recognition, as well as the perception of the meanings of the studied lexical and grammatical phenomena in various contextual circumstances;
- skills aimed at semantization of little-studied words;
- skills aimed at understanding the compositional-semantic texture of a literary text;

- skills aimed at discovering the extensive semantic distinctive features of the text;
- skills aimed at discovering the stylistic distinctive features of the text.

Perception and understanding are considered the main currents in communicative reading. Three degrees of understanding of a foreign language text are emphasized:

- understanding of linguistic information;
- perception of massive, factual information;
- perception of semantic load.

In the methodology, the accentuation of the varieties of reading is carried out taking into account its psychological side, teaching as well as directly methodical conditions. Methodical systematization provides for directly methodical conditions, focusing on the target structure and requirements that characterize educational and speech activity. The basis of methodical systematization is educational reading and communicative reading. It is important to highlight that all types of reading, without exception, are interconnected, they are intertwined, and also expand each other. The rational technology of teaching reading must be built taking into account absolutely all the noted classifications of reading, and the use of various types of reading in the training course is considered a means of accomplishing a single mission - teaching reading in a foreign language. The formation of communicative reading skills is one of the key goals of teaching a foreign language. Communicative reading is an activity according to perception to comprehend what is read on the basis of the independent use of operations of a receptive nature, as

well as actions (skill techniques) intended for the implementation of actions. As well as a kind of training work, communicative reading in a holistic sense is characterized by the same distinctive features, that is, that each work, i.e. contains a task, a reason, specific methods for performing operations aimed at the result of a specific outcome, but they have a peculiar look. Communicative reading is characterized by the automation of reading technique and a significant degree of formation of receptive lexical and grammatical abilities, which guarantees the focus of attention on the content of what is being read, the flexibility of combining techniques that are adequate to a specific reading task [2].

As well as in foreign, so in our methodology, within the framework of the communicative layout, the classification of varieties of communicative reading is created taking into account a specific communicative task, construction on the level of completeness, as well as the accuracy of extracting information that determines the type of reading course, which has acquired particular importance and promotion. This systematization directly reflects types of reading. In the course of teaching reading, the target structure, as well as the main component of speech work, including reading, is created in the form of a task. This task is based on the nature of the text for the purpose of reading and establishes the level of penetration into its content. In methodical publications, detailed terms have gained maximum distribution: reading with partial extraction of information, reading with an understanding of the main content, as well as reading with an absolute understanding of the text.

Reading with selective extraction of information is a type of communicative reading, focused on the discovery of specific information in the text with a view to its further application for specific purposes. This information can be in two varieties:

1. certain information that should be revealed in the text: definitions, dates, numbers, names, as well as titles, or the most detailed information in the display option, argumentation, laws, evaluating opinions. S.K. Folomkina calls reading with the construction to search for certain data of search reading. In the training course, the task that precedes the search reading shows certain information that the student will have to determine by referring to the text. Possessing an accurate understanding of the mission of search reading, the reader is able to foresee whether it is necessary to find the necessary information in one or another part of the text and in what version it will be presented: in numerical formulation, in the form of dates or proper names. Clues for the purpose of quickly retaining the desired information have every chance of being the connecting components of the discourse and other control units of the text.

2. information about the usefulness of the text, whether it is of interest and whether it can be applied in the future. In order to extract this information, it happens quite often to read the headings and subheadings, to get acquainted with the structure of the text in separate paragraphs. Reading in order to acquire the most unified understanding of the content of the word and to

select the necessary resource from some S.K. Folomkina calls viewing. This type of reading implies the display of publications of various sizes (from fragments of a word up to full notes and books) and is also used to a greater extent in research and professional activities. Scanning reading can precede learning reading, in which case it is reading with an absolute understanding of the text. Training tasks during viewing reading have every chance to be appropriate: to find the text according to this problem, the fragment in which the necessary information is located; skim through the text, and also underline paragraphs that do not provide the necessary information. Since the meaning of reading with selective data extraction is the rapid search and finding of the necessary information, in this case, preparation in this version of speech work is usually limited according to time and can occur as well as rivalry among students. The main educational and speech actions performed in this case are considered to be the effects of search, identification, selection, and comparison [3].

Reading with understanding of the main content, with the extraction of the main information - a type of communicative reading with a single girth of content and a structure for understanding the key, more significant - introductory reading. Secondary, unimportant facts have every chance of being obscure, unimportant components have every chance of being missed. During introductory reading, "it is sufficient to present 70% of the text, if the remaining 30% do not include the main statements of the text that are significant in order to comprehend the main content." In the course of introductory reading, synthesis dominates analysis; the language model is in no way considered a subject of free interest. To a greater extent than others, this type of reading will require a connection with the structure and communicative tendency of a single text and its elements, that the first and final paragraphs contain the most important information presented in a concise version. Reading with an understanding of the main content implies the formation of such individual skills, as well as the ability to establish a topic, note the main idea, pick up the main data from the text, omitting not so important ones. In the course of teaching this type of action, students learn to predict the content of the text according to the title, the basis of the text; emphasize semantic milestones in the text, as well as supports; assume the meaning of the main words and skip unfamiliar phrases that do not interfere with the comprehension of the main content.

The most priority trends characterizing the communicative aspect of teaching English are: the impact of conceptual elements on content; selection and organization of training language and speech material used; forecasting in the training course of situations of communication and methods for developing the speech abilities of students; analysis, as well as management of training activities in classes with a teacher and in independent work. Speech work in the property of the concept is considered equally as a necessary and integral part of a single work. Systematizing speech activity, it is necessary to highlight what is important for the purpose of teaching and communicating in English, as well as special, and thus interconnected training in types of

speech activity, in this amount utterance, perception, reading and writing. The classification of communication involves the study of the content, structure and interaction of the communicative, dialogue, as well as perceptual aspects. Of great interest for the purpose of teaching English communication involves the study of a combination of speech and non-verbal means of communication (facial expressions, gestures, body movements, etc.), taking into account their national and cultural characteristics. The classification of the linguistic material used for the purpose of teaching English implies the use of the whole display of the phonetic, lexical and grammatical aspects of the language, and thus the information of communicative linguistics, functional grammar, and contrastive linguistics [4].

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